

IN-SILICO PREDICTION AND DOCKING STUDIES OF NOVEL BENZOXAZOLE DERIVATIVES FOR ANTI-BACTERIAL ACTIVITY**¹*Vidya Shree, ²Dr. Syed Azhar Nizami, ³Dr. Gurumurthy M.**¹Assistant Professor, Ikon College of Pharmacy, Bangalore Dist., Karnataka.²Professor, Dr. H. L. T. College of Pharmacy, Kengal, Channapatana.,
Ramnagram, Dist., Karnataka.Article Received on 10 Oct. 2025,
Article Revised on 30 October 2025,
Article Published on 01 Nov. 2025,<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17539111>***Corresponding Author****Vidya Shree**Assistant Professor, Ikon College of
Pharmacy, Bangalore Dist., Karnataka.**How to cite this Article:** Vidya Shree, Dr. Syed Azhar Nizami, Dr. Gurumurthy M., (2025). *In-Silico Prediction And Docking Studies Of Novel Benzoxazole Derivatives For Anti-Bacterial Activity*. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(11), 762–774.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Objective: The objective of this study was to synthesize, characterized and molecular docking of some novel Benzoxazole derivatives for antibacterial activity. **Methods:** Compounds was synthesized by Claisen-Schmidt condensation method followed by purification by TLC and characterization by FT-IR, ¹HNMR and MASS spectra. The synthesized compounds was docked with target *E.coli* dihydropteroate synthase analogs **pdb (1AJ2)** to check the molecular interaction with enzyme. The compounds were also screened for antibacterial activity using 2 Gram +ve and 2 Gram –ve bacteria by cup plate method. Ciprofloxacin was used as standard. **Results:** We have estimated the result in the form of binding energy. Novel molecules were favoured on the basis of lowest binding energy (–5.076 and –8.956 kcal/mol). All the novel Benzoxazole derivatives (**1a-1e**) were shown more negative energy. On the basis of our studies these all compound

may be valuable Pharmacophore against antibacterial activity. In silico studies predicted for physiochemical properties, ADME, Toxicity and drug likeness. **Summary:** The more negative values indicate a higher binding affinity. The generated ligand observations can be visualized. Physical constants of synthesized derivate such as solubility and melting point were determined. Bioactivity scores were noted for different derivatives and predicted percentage absorption in the gut. The antibacterial activity was performed using the MIC

method (aerobic). **Conclusion:** The present study suggests that novel benzoxazole derivatives can be useful as antibacterial agents.

KEYWORDS: Benzoxazole, Antibacterial activity, SWISS Dock, Auto dock vina, Molsoft, Protox-3.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are a large number of synthetic heterocyclic compounds with important applications in pharmacy, medicines, biotechnology, agriculture, petro-chemical industry and other fields.^[1] A heterocyclic ring may comprise of three or more atoms which may be saturated or unsaturated. Also the ring may contain more than one heteroatom, Nitrogen, Oxygen and Sulfur, which may be similar or dissimilar. The most prominent biologically active heterocyclic compounds contain furan, thiophene, pyridine, quinoline, indole, purine, and other ring systems.^[2,3] Benzoxazole, is a fused ring heterocyclic compound containing a 1,3-oxazole system fused with a benzene ring, it has a profound effect on medicinal chemistry research owing to its important pharmacological activities.^[4-6]

Benzoxazoles also known as benzo[d]oxazoles or 1,3-benzoxazoles, are an important class of π -electron-excessive, benzene-fused heterocyclic compounds. Some reactions of benzoxazoles occur analogous to that of oxazoles, mainly due to the N-atom's electronegativity: salt formation and quarterisation occur at the ring nitrogen; electrophilic substitutions (e.g. nitration or halogenation) takes place on the benzene ring on the 5- or 6-position (the latter the preferred site) and nucleophilic attack occurs at the 2-position. Due to this, nucleophilic substitutions of 2-halobenzoxazoles also take place very easily.^[7-10]

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

All the chemicals used to synthesize the title compounds (Novel benzoxazole derivatives) were of laboratory grade and purchased from S.D. Fine Chemicals and Sigma Aldrich. All the reactions were monitored using Thin Layer Chromatography. The appropriate mobile

phases (Solvent system for TLC) as applicable were developed using silica Gel G, as stationary phase. The FT-IR spectra were recorded by using JASCO FT-IR spectrophotometer V- 430+. All the proton NMR spectra were recorded by using ¹H NMR spectrophotometer on Jeol at 400MHz frequency using DMSO solvent. The GC-MS spectra of all synthesised compound were recorded by using ESI Mass Spectroscopy (IISC). All the compounds considered for biological evaluation were prepared by standard methods as outlined in scheme. The culture used for biological evaluation was purchased from IISC, Biological and evaluation was done by laminar flow.

All molecular docking studies were performed on a Windows 10-based system with Intel Core i5 (8th Gen) processor, 16 GB RAM, using AutoDock Vina version 1.5.6, Swiss dock molinspiration, and protox.

2.1. Target protein preparation: The in-silico antibacterial activity of the synthesized compounds was screened using crystal structure against the target E.coli dihydropteroate synthase analogs pdb (**1AJ2**).

2.1.1. Preparation of ligand

The 2D structure of the ligand was drawn using ChemDraw/ChemSketch, and then the molecule will appear in the text box in SMILES notation and will be drawn in the molecular sketcher. Once selected a ligand, the "Prepare ligand" button was appeared in red and active. A check mark was appeared next to the button and the preparation was successful.

2.1.2. Preparation of protein

Submitted the target by writing a PDB ID-**1AJ2**, uploading a PDB file (and a PDBQT file for Vina). Then we selected chain(s) and heteroatom(s) to keep for the docking. Once selected the target, the "Prepare target" button was appeared in red and active A check mark was appeared next to the button and the preparation was successful.

2.1.3. Docking

The search space in which the ligand to be docked was selected. Once successfully prepared ligand and a target was selected "Check parameters" button will become red and active. This will check the docking input is OK and estimated the calculation time. Once the checked and validated the "START DOCKING" button becomes red and active. Then docking was started.

2.1.4. Preparation of 1-(4-(benzoxazole-2-yl) phenyl) ethanone

0.01 mole of Benzoxazole (0.119 gm) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (25 mL) and 0.154 gm of 1-(4-chlorophenyl) ethanone (0.1mole) was added. The mixture was refluxed with condenser in synthetic microwave oven at 160 Watts for 40 minutes. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool at room temperature, and then poured on to crushed ice with occasional stirring. The precipitate obtained is filtered, washed with water and dried.

2.1.5. Preparation of 1-(4-(benzoxazole-2-yl) phenyl)-3-phenyl prop-2-en-1-one.(1a-e)

A mixture of 1-(4-(benzoxazol-2-yl) phenyl) ethanone (0.1 mol) 0.274 g and aromatic aldehydes (0.01 mol) was stirred in 90 % ethanol (30 mL) and then an aqueous solution of Alcoholic KOH (40%, 15 mL) added to it. The mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and then it was poured onto crushed ice, stirred and acidified with dil. HCl. The solid separated was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol.

2.1.6. Antibacterial Activity

The compounds synthesized during the present investigation were screened for their antibacterial activity. The antibacterial tests were conducted on four common microorganisms such as *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which are the representative types of gram positive and gram-negative organisms respectively. The antibacterial activity of the compounds was assessed by disc diffusion method.

2.1.7. Method of testing

The sterilized media was cooled to 45 °C with gentle shaking to bring about uniform cooling and then inoculated with 18-24 h old culture under aseptic conditions, mixed well by gentle shaking. This was poured into sterile Petri dishes and allowed the medium to set. After solidification all the Petri dishes were transferred to laminar air flow unit. Then the discs which were previously prepared were carefully kept on the solidified media by using sterilized forceps. These Petri dishes were kept as it is for one hour for diffusion at room temperature and then for incubation at 37 °C for 24 h in an incubator. The extent diameter of inhibition after 24 hrs was measured as the zone of inhibition in millimeters and the results were shown in Table No-4.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All the synthesized compounds remitted good yield. The Purity of all the synthesized compounds was checked by their melting point as well as TLC. The structure of synthesized compounds have been established and confirmed by spectral and elemental data obtained viz, FT-IR, ¹HNMR and Mass spectroscopy. (Fig no 1 and Table no 1).

Fig. No. 1: scheme 01. Preparation of -(4-(benzoxazole-2-yl) phenyl)-3-phenyl prop-2-en-1-one. 1a-1e.

Table No. 1: Physical properties and Spectral data analysis of compounds 1a-e.

Comp code	Structures	Description
1a	<p>1a- 1-(4-(benzoxazol-2-yl)phenyl)-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-one</p>	Mol. Formula. C ₂₂ H ₁₅ NO ₂ , Relative Mass 325.11 Melting Point °C, 199-202, % yield , 61, Rf Value 0.47. IR-Spectra KBr cm⁻¹. 3250.6, (N-H str), 1620.0, (C=O str), 1530.4, (CH=CH def), 1485.9, (CH-CH str) 1090.3, (C-O-C). ¹H NMR (δ ppm). 7.43-6.36 (m, 13H, C-H aromatic), 7.44 (2H, CH=CH for chalcones), 7.50 (s, 1H aromatic, N-H).
1b	<p>1b- 1-(4-(benzoxazol-2-yl)phenyl)-3-(2-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one</p>	Mol. Formula. C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ClNO ₂ , Relative Mass 359.06, Melting point , 198-199, % yield , 76, Rf value , 0.80. IR-Spectra KBr cm⁻¹. 3250.6, (N-H str), 1620.0, (C=O str), 1530.4, (CH=CH def), 1480.2, (CH-CH str) 1050.4, (C-O-C), 738.7.1 (C-Cl str). ¹H NMR (δ ppm). 7.36-6.36 (m, 12H, C-H aromatic), 7.44-7.42 (2H, CH=CH for chalcones), 7.63 (s, 1H aromatic, N-H).

<p>1c</p> <p>1c- 1-(4-(benzoxazol-2-yl)phenyl)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one</p>		<p>Mol. Formula $C_{22}H_{15}NO_3$, Relative Mass 341.11 Melting point, 201-203, % yield 62, Rf value 0.61. IR-Spectra KBr cm-1. 3390.3 (OH-str aromatic), 3150.4, (N-H str), 1620.0, (C=O str), 1530.4, (CH=CH def), 1480.6, (CH-CH str) 1080.5, (C-O-C). 1H NMR (δ ppm). 7.36-6.36 (m, 11H, C-H aromatic), 7.44-7.42 (2H, CH=CH for chalcones), 7.63 (s, 1H aromatic, N-H), 5.21 (s, 1H-OH).</p>
<p>1d</p> <p>1d- 1-(4-(benzoxazol-2-yl)phenyl)-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one</p>		<p>Mol. Formula. $C_{22}H_{15}NO_3$, Relative Mass. 341.11 Melting point, 201-204, % yield. 66, Rf value, 0.43. IR-Spectra KBr cm-1. 3390.3 (OH-str aromatic), 3150.4, (N-H str), 1620.0, (C=O str), 1530.4, (CH=CH def), 1485.9, (CH-CH str) 1090.3, (C-O-C). 1H NMR (δ ppm). 7.36-6.36 (m, 11H, C-H aromatic), 7.44-7.42 (2H, CH=CH for chalcones), 7.63 (s, 1H aromatic, N-H), 5.21 (s, 1H-OH).</p>
<p>1e</p> <p>1e- 1-(4-(benzoxazol-2-yl)phenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one</p>		<p>Mol. Formula $C_{23}H_{17}NO_3$ Relative Mass 355.12 Melting point, 200-203, % yield 68, Rf value 0.40. IR-Spectra KBr cm-1, 3250.6, (N-H str), 1620.0, (C=O str), 1530.4, (CH=CH def), 1460.2, (CH-CH str), 1180.3(OCH3-str), 1001.3, (C-O-C). 1H NMR (δ ppm). 7.36-6.36 (m, 11H, C-H aromatic), 7.44-7.42 (2H, CH=CH for chalcones), 7.63 (s, 1H aromatic, N-H), 3.24-3.35 (s, 3H-OCH3).</p>

Toxicity Model Report

Copy | Excel | CSV | PDF

Classification	Target	Shorthand	Prediction	Probability
Organ toxicity	Hepatotoxicity	dili	Inactive	0.51
Organ toxicity	Nephrotoxicity	nephro	Inactive	0.74
Toxicity end points	Carcinogenicity	carcino	Inactive	0.66
Toxicity end points	Mutagenicity	mutagen	Inactive	0.67

The toxicity radar chart is intended to quickly illustrate the confidence of positive toxicity results compared to the average of its class.

Click the thumbnail to access the plot once it has finished loading.

Toxicity Model Report

Copy | Excel | CSV | PDF

Classification	Target	Shorthand	Prediction	Probability
Organ toxicity	Hepatotoxicity	dili	Inactive	0.51
Organ toxicity	Nephrotoxicity	nephro	Inactive	0.74
Toxicity end points	Carcinogenicity	carcino	Inactive	0.66
Toxicity end points	Mutagenicity	mutagen	Inactive	0.67

The toxicity radar chart is intended to quickly illustrate the confidence of positive toxicity results compared to the average of its class.

Click the thumbnail to access the plot once it has finished loading.

Toxicity Model Report

Copy | Excel | CSV | PDF

Classification	Target	Shorthand	Prediction	Probability
Organ toxicity	Hepatotoxicity	dili	Inactive	0.61
Organ toxicity	Nephrotoxicity	nephro	Inactive	0.63
Toxicity end points	Carcinogenicity	carcino	Inactive	0.59
Toxicity end points	Mutagenicity	mutagen	Inactive	0.59

The toxicity radar chart is intended to quickly illustrate the confidence of positive toxicity results compared to the average of its class.

Click the thumbnail to access the plot once it has finished loading.

Toxicity Model Report

Copy | Excel | CSV | PDF

Classification	Target	Shorthand	Prediction	Probability
Organ toxicity	Hepatotoxicity	dili	Inactive	0.57
Organ toxicity	Nephrotoxicity	nephro	Inactive	0.52
Toxicity end points	Carcinogenicity	carcino	Inactive	0.60
Toxicity end points	Mutagenicity	mutagen	Inactive	0.54

The toxicity radar chart is intended to quickly illustrate the confidence of positive toxicity results compared to the average of its class.

Click the thumbnail to access the plot once it has finished loading.

Toxicity Model Report

Copy | Excel | CSV | PDF

Classification	Target	Shorthand	Prediction	Probability
Organ toxicity	Hepatotoxicity	dili	Inactive	0.54
Organ toxicity	Nephrotoxicity	nephro	Inactive	0.66
Toxicity end points	Carcinogenicity	carcino	Inactive	0.59
Toxicity end points	Mutagenicity	mutagen	Inactive	0.53

The toxicity radar chart is intended to quickly illustrate the confidence of positive toxicity results compared to the average of its class.

Click the thumbnail to access the plot once it has finished loading.

(ADMET) prediction of compounds 1a-1e:

Entry	MiLog P	%ABS	TPSA	MW	nON accptr	ONHOH Donor	Lipinski violation	nRotb	Mv
Rule	1.5	-	-	<500	<10	<5	<1	-	-
1a	3.63	98.84	29.43	279.36	2	0	0	3	249.2
1b	4.08	98.84	29.43	313.81	2	0	0	3	262.7
1c	3.39	91.86	49.66	295.36	3	1	0	3	257.2
1d	3.15	91.86	49.66	295.36	3	1	0	3	257.2
1e	3.69	95.65	38.67	309.39	3	0	0	4	312.1

miLog-P Liphophilicity expressed as LOG-P, %AB – Absorption percentage, M.W-molecular weight in gm/mol, T P S A- Topological polar surface area, nON , no of O-N acceptor, ONHOH, No of ONHOH donor, n rotb- number of rotatable bond, nLV- Lipinski violation, MV Molar volumes.

$$[\% \text{-AB} = 109 - (0.345 \times \text{TPSA})]$$

Fig. No. 2: ADME prediction toxicity model report for compounds 1a-1e.

Table no 2: Insilico toxicity prediction of comp (1a-e).

Comp Code	Hepatotoxicity	Nephrotoxicity	Carcinogenicity	Mutagenicity	Predicted LD50{mg/kg}
1a	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	2500
1b	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	2500
1c	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	2500
1d	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	2500
1e	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	Inactive	2500

The results shown figure no 2 and table no 2 that compounds 1a-1e shows the log p value 3.15 - 4.08, and all compounds show TPSA less than 150 Å⁰ indicating a good permeability of drug in the cellular plasma membrane. %ABS means percentage absorption which in the range of 91.86–98.84% signifying good absorption in the intestine. Insilico toxicity prediction shows inactive against Hepatotoxicity, Nephrotoxicity, Carcinogenicity, Mutagenicity the probability score was less than 1.

Fig. No. 3: Molecular docking of Ciprofloxacin with pdb 1aj2.

Docking of 1a on protein surface of pdb-1aj2

Molecular Docking of 1a with pdb-1aj2

Molecular Docking of 1b with pdb-1aj2

Molecular Docking of 1c with pdb-1aj2

Molecular Docking of 1d with pdb-1aj2

Molecular Docking of 1e with pdb-1aj2

Fig. no. 4: Docking interaction Ciprofloxacin and 1a-1e with E.coli dihydropteroate synthase analogs pdb (1AJ2).

Table no. 3: Docking interaction Ciprofloxacin and 1a-1e with E.coli dihydropteroate synthase analogs pdb (1AJ2).

Ligand	PDB Id	Binding Interactions		Binding Energies	Interacting residues
				(Kcalories/mol)	
Ciprofloxacin	1AJ2	No of Hydrogen bond	02	-6.256 -8.653	ARG-A:255-Ligand-N GLY-A:217-Ligand-N
		Hydrophobic Interactions	02	-5.432 -7.641	PHE-A:190-Ligand-C ARG-A:220-Ligand-F
		Pi-Pi interaction	01	-6.654	LYS-A:221-Ligand-N
1a	1AJ2	No of Hydrogen bond	01	-7.231	VAL-A:161-Ligand-O
		Hydrophobic Interactions	06	-8.643 -6.761 -6.554 -7.128 -6.741 -7.541	ALA-A:151-Ligand-C LEU-A:215-Ligand-C ILE-A:17-Ligand-C ARG-A:63-Ligand-C ARG-A:220-Ligand-C PRO-A:232-Ligand-C
		Pi-Pi interaction	01	-8.219	ARG-A:63-Ligand-O
1b	1AJ2	No of Hydrogen bond	01	-7.244	THR-A:62-Ligand-O
		Hydrophobic Interactions	05	-6.116 -7.531 -7.761 -8.831	ILE-A:117-Ligand-C PHE-A:190-Ligand-C ARG-A:220-Ligand-C LEU-A:215-Ligand-C
		Pi-Pi interaction	02	-6.256 -5.321	ASP-A:96-Ligand-C1 ARG-A:63-Ligand-O
1c	1AJ2	No of Hydrogen bond	03	-5.240 -7.651	ASP-A:185-Ligand-O ASN-A:115-Ligand-O
		Hydrophobic Interactions	04	-6.872 -7.531 -8.091 -7.421	ILE-A:117-Ligand-C ARG-A:220-Ligand-C PRO-A:232-Ligand-C PHE-A:190-Ligand-C
		Pi-Pi interaction	02	-7.756 -8.431	LYS-A:221-Ligand-Pi-C ARG-A:63-Ligand-Pi-C
1d	1AJ2	No of Hydrogen bond	03	-8.235 -5.821 -7.221	ASP-A:185-Ligand-O ASN-A:115-Ligand-O ARG-A:63-Ligand-O
		Hydrophobic Interactions	02	-5.298	LEU-A:273-Ligand-C PHE-A:190-Ligand-C
		Pi-Pi interaction	01	-6.298	ARG-A:63-Ligand-Pi-C
1e	1AJ2	No of Hydrogen bond	01	-5.287	THR-A:62-Ligand-O
		Hydrophobic Interactions	04	-8.956 -7.721 -6.651 -5.706	LEU-A:215-Ligand-C ILE-A:117-Ligand-C ARG-A:220-Ligand-C ARG-A:63-Ligand-C
		Pi-Pi interaction	01	-7.217	ARG-A:63-Ligand-Pi-C

3.1. Antibacterial activity

All the synthesized compounds were screened for antibacterial activity studies at a concentration of 100 µg/ml using DMF as a control against *B.subtilis*, *B.pumilus*, *E.coli* and *P.aeruginosa* respectively by disc diffusion method on nutrient agar media, Ciprofloxacin 100 µg/ml was used as standard against Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. The results are reported in table no 4.

Table No. 4: Anti-bacterial activity of synthesized compounds (1a-1e).

Sample Code	*Inhibition of zone diameter in mm			
	<i>B.subtilis</i>	<i>B.pumilus</i>	<i>E.coli</i>	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>
	100 µg/ml	100 µg/ml	100 µg/ml	100 µg/ml
1a	28 ± 1.12	23± 1.15	21 ± 1.22	20± 1.60
1b	25 ± 1.21	23± 1.72	20 ± 1.14	23± 1.12
1c	23 ± 1.06	21 ± 1.55	20± 1.21	21± 1.33
1d	20 ± 1.24	18 ± 1.22	18± 1.28	13 ± 1.31
1e	26± 1.20	22± 1.08	27± 1.44	21± 1.18
Standard Ciprofloxacin	30 ± 1.20	27 ± 1.29	30 ± 1.17	27 ± 1.22
DMF	-	-	-	-

*Each value is an average of three independent determination ± Standard deviation.

3.2. DISCUSSION

All synthesized compounds showed good binding affinities lesser or higher than the standard drug ciprofloxacin. However, compound **1a**, **1d**, **1c** and **1e** had exhibited the highest binding affinity with a docking score of -5.076 and -8.956 kcal/mol respectively, against target protein PDB ID: 1AJ2. This is in comparison to the standard drug ciprofloxacin ligand, which showed docking, scores of -5.432 and -8.865 kcal/mol respectively. Compound 1a displayed strong conventional hydrophobic interactions with interacting amino acids ALA-A: 151-Ligand-C, LEU-A: 215-Ligand-C, ILE-A: 17-Ligand-C, ARG-A: 63-Ligand-C, ARG-A: 220-Ligand-C, PRO-A: 232-Ligand-C respectively. In contrast, ciprofloxacin interacted with PHE-A: 190-Ligand-C, ARG-A: 220-Ligand-F. The data in the Table No-7 indicate that compound **1a** was found to possess a significant activity against *Bacillus subtilis* and also compound **1b** and **1d** shown significant activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, compounds **1b** and **1e** showed good activity against *E.coli* and *Bacillus pumilus* rest of the compounds were found to exhibit poor activity when compared to the standard Ciprofloxacin. From the anti-bacterial screening it was found that the compounds showed moderate to weak activity. The compounds were found to possess good activity against some of the organisms

used for the study, rest of the compounds were found to exhibit weak activities when compared to standard Ciprofloxacin, which produced maximum zone of Inhibition.

4. CONCLUSION

In this research work we have synthesized some new novel benzoxazole derivatives. The structures of the title compounds were elucidated and confirmed through spectral analysis using IR, ¹H NMR, and LC-MS spectroscopy. All synthesized compounds were screened for in-silico studies utilizing various online tools, including Swiss ADME, Molinspiration, and ProTox-3. All compounds complied with Lipinski's rule of five. Additionally, all compounds exhibited suitable ADME properties, indicating their potential as drug candidates. The compounds (**1a-e**) were docked against the target E.coli dihydropteroate synthase analogs PDB (**1AJ2**). Molecular docking studies of the active compounds revealed that these compounds might act via inhibition E.coli dihydropteroate synthase analogs PDB (**1AJ2**) which were found with excellent interactions in a superimposed complex. The synthesized compounds (**1a-e**) were screened for their antibacterial activity. Ciprofloxacin 100 µg/ml was used as standard drug. The findings indicated that the test compounds showed least to good activity against standard Ciprofloxacin. Altogether, these results show that some novel benzoxazole derivatives have fair antibacterial activity.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author is thankful to chairman and principal of Dr HLT college of pharmacy for providing necessary facilities and help in carrying out this project work.

6. REFERENCES

1. J. Robinson, S. Kingman, D. Irvine, P. Licence, A. Smith, G. Dimitrakis, D. Obermayer, and C. O. Kappe, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys. PCCP*, 2010; 12: 4750–58.
2. Larhed M, Hallberg A. Microwave-assisted high-speed chemistry: a new technique in drug discovery, *Drug Discov Today*, 2001; 6(8): 406-416.
3. Lew A, Krutzik PO, Hart ME, Chamberlin AR. Increasing rates of reaction: microwave-assisted organic synthesis for combinatorial chemistry, *J Comb Chem*, 2002; 4(2): 95-105 22.
4. Mohammad poor-Baltorka M, Moghadama S, Tangestaninejada V, Mirkhania et al. Silica Sulfuric Acid Catalyzed Synthesis of Benzoxazoles, Benzimidazoles and Oxazolo [4, 5-b] pyridines Under Heterogeneous and Solvent-Free Conditions. *J Iran Chem Soc.*, 2008; (5): S65S70.

5. Saritha Garrepalli, Manne Pavan Kumar, Ambati Praneeth Sai, Bommalla Sharanya, Ganneboina Jyothir Mai, Chikoti Abhinavgandhi, et al. Synthesis and biological evaluation of benzoxazole derivatives as new anti-inflammatory agents, *International Journal of Biopharmaceutics.*, 2012; 3(1): 50-54.
6. Synthesis of Some Novel Benzoxazole Derivatives as Anticancer, Anti-Hiv-1 and Antimicrobial Agents, SM Rida et al. *Eur J Med Chem.*, 2005; 40(9): 949-959.
7. Froehr T, Sindlinger CP, Kloeckner U, Finkbeiner P, Nachtsheim BJ. Synthesis of 1,3-oxazoles and benzoxazoles, *Organic Chemistry Portal Org. Lett.*, 2011; 13: 3754-3757.
8. Ramanatham Vinod Kumar. Synthetic Strategies towards Benzoxazole Ring System: A Review, *Asian Journal of Chemistry*, 2004; 16(3-4): 1241-1260.
9. Moghaddam FM, Bardajee GR, Ismaili H, Taimoory SMD. Facile and efficient one pot protocol for the synthesis of benzoxazole and benzthiazole derivative using molecular iodine as a catalyst. *Bioorg Med Chem.*, 1997; 5: 655-9.
10. Unlu S, Baytas SN, Kupeli E, Yesilada E. Studies on novel 7-acyl-5-chloro-2-oxo-3H-benzoxazole derivatives as potential analgesic and antiinflammatory agents. *Arch Pharm.*, 2003; 336: 3 10-21.